

DETECTION OF DAMAGES ON COMPOSITE PLATES DUE TO LOW VELOCITY IMPACT USING CARBON FIBERS

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Introduction

- Aim of this study is to help understanding the behavior of carbon fiber sensor and investigating its mechanical and piezoresistive features.
- Carbon fiber sensor can be used with different patch materials like Glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) and Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP).
- Performance of carbon fibers was tested under low velocity impact loading to gain better understanding towards the development of a reliable sensor that can be used to monitor damages in composite structures
- To test the capability of carbon fibers to detect impact loadings.
- To investigate the capability of CF sensor to monitor the response of the structure due to these disturbances.

Experimental work

- In the current work, the type of carbon fibers used are Toray T300b.
- The selection of Toray T300b was based their linear piezoresistivity and successful use of them for strain measurement in previous studies.
- Tensile tests were performed to get the relationship between the resistance and strain level of the sensor which facilitated the use of the sensor in detecting low velocity impact.
- The information collected from the tensile tests was used to characterize the damage inflicted on a composite plate.
- A composite plate was impacted and the carbon fiber sensor was placed near the area of impact, where the maximum strains were induced.
- Consequently, the strains induced by the impact caused a change in resistance which was measured by the ohmmeter.
- By performing the experiment at different impact energies, sensor's response at different energy levels was observed and the limit which would cause failure in the composite plate identified. The resistance output at this energy was recorded and set as threshold which indicates the failure point of the plate. Thus, whenever the output of the sensor is close to this value, there is a risk of breaking in the plate.

Composite plate with embedded sensor

Dent left from the strike using impact energy of 10J

Carbon Fiber with springs on metallic bed.

Results

- The task here is to observe the performance of the sensor due to an impact test.
- Impact tests were carried out on composite plates embedded with one carbon fiber sensor
- Experiments were repeated with different values of impact energies to observe how sensor's output varies with different magnitudes of impact force on the plate. Five different values of impact energies were chosen: 5J, 6J, 7J, 8J and 10J.
- The results show that the change in resistance of the carbon fiber sensor closely follows that of deflection
- The deflection of the plates due to different impact energies is plotted in a single graph and the corresponding response of the carbon fiber sensor for the mentioned impact energies was recorded and is plotted.

Deflection plots of all five impact tests

Carbon fiber sensor output for five different impact energies

Deflection and energy curve for 5 J impact. Black curve: deflection. Red curve: energy

Plot of deflection vs time vs ΔR/R %

Conclusion

- An application of the carbon fiber sensor is its use in structures to detect damage. Therefore, impact tests were carried out on composite plates in which the carbon fiber sensors were embedded.
- The results show that carbon fiber sensor can successfully predict the damage based on the resulting strains developed in the composite plate. Hence showing us that carbon fiber sensors can be used in structural health monitoring of composite materials.

References

- Bashmal S, Siddiqui M, Arif AF. Experimental and Numerical Investigations on the Mechanical Characteristics of Carbon Fiber Sensors. *Sensors*. 2017;17(9):2026.
- Hu, N.: Composites and Their Applications. (2012)
- Smith, R.: Composite Defects and Their Detection. *Materials Science and Engineering*. III, (1997)
- Cai, J., Qiu, L., Yuan, S., Shi, L., Liu, P., Liang, D.: Structural Health Monitoring for Composite Materials. 37–60 (2012)
- Chib, A.: Parametric study of low velocity impact analysis on composite tubes. ... *Composites Conference & ...* (2006)
- Sohn, H., Farrar, C.R., Hemez, F.M., Shunk, D.D., Stinemates, D.W., Nadler, B.R., Czarnecki, J.J.: A Review of Structural Health Monitoring Literature : 1996 – 2001. 1996–2001 (2004). doi:LA-13976-MS
- Takeda, S., Minakuchi, S., Okabe, Y., Takeda, N.: Delamination monitoring of laminated composites subjected to low-velocity impact using small-diameter FBG sensors. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 36, 903–908 (2005). doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2004.12.005